

CRITERIA FOR PREPARING FUTURE TEACHERS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF NATIONAL AND GENERAL CULTURAL COMPETENCIES IN STUDENTS

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada bo'lajak o'qituvchilarni o'quvchilarda milliy va umummadaniy kompetensiyalarni rivojlantirishga tayyorlash mezonlari o'rganilgan, uning bugungi kundagi zarurati hamda pedagogik asoslari atroflicha yoritilgan.

Abstract: In this article, the forms of preparation of future teachers for the development of national and general cultural competences in students are studied, its necessity and pedagogical foundations are detailed.

Key words: pedagogue, professional competence, classification, improvement, competence, competent approach, national and general cultural competences.

INTRODUCTION. Today, tolerant and fruitful intercultural relations based on sincerity for all humanity are a guarantee of peace and harmony in the international arena. In the Millennium Declaration of the United Nations, "people must respect each other despite the diversity of their religious beliefs, cultures and languages. Differences within and between communities should not be alarming, and should not be grounds for persecution. Perhaps it should be preserved as the most valuable wealth of mankind. World culture and dialogue between all civilizations should be actively encouraged", there is also a call to create an atmosphere of tolerance in intercultural relations. Therefore, it is becoming necessary for every country to support cultural dialogue based on mutual trust.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. Issues of development of socio-cultural activity among future teachers in Uzbekistan M. Rakhmanova, M. Kuronov, H. Tojiboyeva, G.J. Tulenova, Q. Quranboyev; N. Abdumuratova, D. Nafasov regarding the development of socio-cultural competence; historical-philosophical, ethical-aesthetic content of spiritual and artistic values, O. Abdurakhmonov, D. Yakibova, R. Mavlonova, N. Rakhmonkulova have conducted studies on the development of thinking capabilities of learners based on the person-oriented approach.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. L.YE.Babushkina, L.I.Karpova express a different opinion on the criteria of general cultural content:

- thematic criterion: having regularly updated historical, social and cultural knowledge about previous historical stages (about the most important events in the life of the countries of the world and their own countries, cultural achievements, etc.) to be
- personal criterion: student's interests, everyday life, constructive and comparative aspects of differences in historical and socio-cultural perception, individual ideas about the history of the country and its spiritual and cultural wealth;
- the criterion of the frequency and variety of contact with socio-cultural events: active social activity, interest in culture and raising one's general cultural level, the process of studying history and applying one's socio-cultural skills to the field of future professional activity the ability to generalize, cultural phenomena available to present in the classroom [3].

Z.A. Aksyutina developed the criteria for evaluating universal competence, which represent social mobility in the work of a future teacher, the expansion of intercultural relations in the professional field, and the integration of the educational space. They are as follows:

- the presence of a complex of theoretical knowledge about the socio-cultural aspects of their subject and their professional socio-cultural activities;
- having practical knowledge of professional socio-cultural communication and means of activity;
- to adapt to the new socio-economic conditions, to form students' ability to sufficiently understand the socio-cultural processes of humanism and tolerance;
- the ability to develop a strategy of communicative behavior that affects the adoption of socio-pedagogical decisions and the results of pedagogical activity;
- availability of modern pedagogical skills, possession of advanced pedagogical technologies, successful application of psychological-pedagogical foundations of knowledge and socio-cultural education [4].

Criterion is the most important features of the studied phenomenon, they harmonize with concepts such as standard and standard and represent its most perfect and important level. Correlating the current situation with it, it is possible to determine and describe their degree of randomness and, therefore, their approximation to the norm.

In the study, the criteria for preparing future teachers for the process of national and general cultural competence development were clarified. They consist of:

- worldview: an important component (structural part) of the teacher's personality and activity, the system of views on the surrounding existence, the establishment of social and cultural behavioral complexes and the personal image of the subject's practical experience and cultural historical experience and the culture to which he belongs;
- cognitive: the existence of a set of theoretical knowledge on professional national and general cultural activities, the ability to constantly fill the knowledge and socio-cultural portfolio, understand historical facts and events, justify and objectively evaluate historical and socio-cultural events;
- motivational-valued: interested, attitude to the subject, national and cultural facts and events, interest, assessment, personal acceptance and assimilation of the spiritual and moral content of historical and national and universal cultural values;
- faoliyatli-uslubiy: o'zining milliy va umummadaniy tajribalariga ega bo'lish va kengaytirish, tavsiflash, tushuntirish, yetarli texnologiyalarni qo'llash, milliy va umummadaniy bilimlarini ta'minlash, axborotlar oqimini boshqarish, respublika va jahondagi siyosiy-tarixiy holatlarni baholashni asoslash, tushunchalar berish;
- practical acquisition of professional pedagogical communication tools.

When describing the obtained result in a certain period of time, the criterion should have a set of measurements, the main characteristics of which are accuracy and ease of observation, accounting and recording.

An indicator is a precise measure of this criterion. An indicator (indicator) in most cases is an object, a process or its result, a concept or a generalized characteristic of their properties, usually expressed in numerical form. When metrics are selected, benchmarks are available to monitor and measure. Specificity as the main characteristic of an indicator allows

it to be considered the most accurate in relation to a criterion, from which it can be concluded that one criterion can have several indicators.

Criterion indicators of preparation of future teachers for the process of development of national and general cultural competence:

Cognitive-intellectual:

- development of analytical work skills with the formation of knowledge about national and general cultural relations;
- the integrity of the national and universal value system;
- problematic vision;
- alternative and different thinking;
- searcher-transformer method.

Motivational:

- interest, curiosity;
- goal orientation;
- achievement motivation;
- social (practical, spiritual) direction.

Emotional:

- emotional reaction to facts, events, situations, cultural works;
- emphasizing important values;
- to experience the ideological, political, moral content of the events.

Creative (creative):

- creative thinking;
- integrity of perception;
- independence;
- the ability to conduct research;
- creating new ideas.

Communicative:

- objective perception of different ideas and views;
- respect the opinions of others;
- teamwork skills;
- communication and discussion culture.

In fact, culture is the internal content of human activity. From this point of view, the main meaning of human activity is to realize oneself as a free creative person, to create a world of humanity bit by bit and to humanize the universe on this basis. Therefore, the "mass culture" that forms the core of consumerism is contrary to the essence of real culture. It is a phenomenon that mentally injures a person, destroys his spiritual world, reduces him to the level of a creature with no other purpose than to save his life, and turns the people into a crowd. That is why such culture can be called "crowd culture".

The specific national and ethnic thinking of representatives of different cultures often appears as an obstacle in intercultural relations. Here, the following aspects of consciousness are of special interest:

- tendency to ethnocentrism - negative assessment of the owner of a foreign culture based on the standards of one's own culture;
- the formation of superficial images in the ethnic mind of one's own culture and representatives of other cultures, that is, stereotyping;

- false perceptions of the process of intercultural relations, including past negative experiences, etc. concern These phenomena were highlighted as strong obstacles in the initial stages of the process of intercultural interaction, where there is no complete information about the identity of the partners [6].

CONCLUSION. In conclusion, the system of interdisciplinary cooperation in the preparation of future teachers for the process of national and universal competence development is not really new to the pedagogical process and educational system. However, it is possible to create a technology for organic and systematic organization of interdisciplinary cooperation and ensure that more students acquire a high culture of communication through independent learning and free expression of opinions. Because today's contradictions in our country and in the international arena can be resolved through experts with deep thinking, broad worldview and quick decision-making skills.

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